

meter shows considerable lateral overlapping of metal and ligand orbitals.

The observed magnetic moment of the Ir^{IV} complex (per metal atom) is 1.76 B.M. (calcd. 1.80 B.M.) which is nearer to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. The first band noted at 18 158 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of this complex is consistent with the Laporte-forbidden ¹t_{1g}Cl_π → ²t_{2g} transition^{11,12}. This is further substantiated by the optical electronegativity of Cl⁻ calculated approximately as 2.9 for the above band using Xopt(M) as 2.3 for octahedral Ir^{IV} ion¹³. The other bands appearing at 23 948, 27 027, 35 087, 36 363 and 38 461 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the E_g⁴T_{1g}, E_g⁴T_{2g}, U_g³A_{2g}, U_g³T_{1g} and E_g^{1,2}T_{1g} states respectively¹⁴. The values of B, C, 10Dq and ζ have been evaluated as 577, 2 308, 42 260 and 4 096 cm⁻¹ respectively. The value of ζ (82% of the free ion value), is suggestive of a slight distortion from the octahedral geometry. This is understandably due to the unequal LF around the metal ion².

The 22 625, 25 641, 28 571 and 40 000 cm⁻¹ bands of the Rh^{III} complex are assignable to the ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, → ¹E_g, → ¹A_{2g} and → ¹T_{2g} transitions respectively¹⁵. Various LF parameters evaluated are B = 714, Dq^{xy} = 3 179, D_q^z = 2 593, D_t = 335, C = 3 223, ρ_{xy}² = 19 174 and ρ_z² = 15 657 cm⁻¹. Obviously, the in-plane ligand field is stronger than the axial one, i.e. the octahedron is distorted with axial elongation. It is concluded that the PBA(N₂) and MeOH(O₂) donor atoms are equatorially placed whereas the two chlorine ligands occupy the axial positions.

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References

1. K. IFTIKHAR, ARVIND, M. SAYEED, S. M. ALI and N. AHMAD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 170.
2. S. M. ALI, K. IFTIKHAR and N. AHMAD, *Synth. React. Inorg. Met.-Org. Chem.*, 1986, 16, 1419.
3. J. I. BULLOCK and H. A. T. RIAHI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1978, 36.
4. M. L. ILLINGSWORTH and R. D. ARCHER, *Polyhedron*, 1982, 1, 487.
5. K. NAKAMOTO "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963, p. 193.
6. A. SYAMAL, D. KUMAR and S. AHMAD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982 21, 634; A. SYAMAL and M. R. MAURYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 26, 1152.
7. K. DEY and R. L. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 1530.
8. H. BASCH and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 365.
9. L. G. VANQUICKENBORNE and A. OEUERMANS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 796.
10. J. R. PERUMAREDDI, A. D. LIEHR and A. W. ADAMSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 249.
11. A. GOURSOT, H. CHERMETTE and C. DAUL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, 23, 305.
12. M. D. ROW, A. J. MCCAFFERY, R. GALE and D. N. COFFEY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 3090.
13. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 244.
14. R. GALE and A. J. MCCAFFERY, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 1944.
15. C. J. BALLHAUSEN "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1967.

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Tellurium(IV) by Periodate in Perchloric Acid Medium

R. RAM BABU, P. VANI,

N. SRI DEVI and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU*

Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry,
School of Chemistry, Andhra University,
Visakhapatnam-530 008

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accepted 22 July 1989

ALTHOUGH the kinetics of oxidation of tellurium(IV) has been studied using a variety of oxidants¹, its mechanism is not yet well-understood. In order to get further insight into the mechanism, the present work reports the results of a detailed kinetic study of its oxidation by periodate in perchloric acid medium. The mechanism of this reaction seems to involve the transfer of an oxygen atom from periodate to tellurium(IV).

Experimental

A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of Te^{IV} was prepared afresh by dissolving sodium tellurite (LR, B.D.H.) in water. A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of Te^{VI} in 2.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid was prepared from sodium tellurate (LR, B.D.H.). Aqueous solutions (0.1 mol dm⁻³) of periodate and iodate were prepared from sodium metaperiodate and potassium iodate (AnalaR) respectively. An approximately 8.0 mol dm⁻³ solution of sodium perchlorate was prepared by neutralising sodium carbonate (AnalaR) with 70% perchloric acid (Merck, pro analysi). All other chemicals used were of AR grade.

Kinetics of the reaction were studied at 60 ± 0.1° in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium keeping [Te^{IV}] in 10-fold excess over [periodate]. The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically following the absorbance of periodate at 280 nm, where it has considerable absorption and all other ions involved in the reaction have negligible absorption. The rate constants were found to be reproducible within ± 5%.

Two- to four-fold excess of periodate was allowed to react with Te^{IV} at 60° in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium. After completion of the reaction, the concentration of the unreacted oxidant was determined spectrophotometrically. The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be in the mole ratio of 1 : 1.

Results and Discussion

The products of the reaction, tellurium(vi) and iodate, do not have any effect on the rate of the reaction. The order with respect to periodate was determined in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid, keeping [Te^{IV}] constant and varying [periodate] in the range 2.5–40.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³. The plots of log [periodate] vs time were found to be linear beyond two half-lives of the reaction, indicating first order dependence on [periodate]. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants (*k'*) obtained at different concentrations of periodate were found to be nearly the same confirming an order of unity in periodate.

The order with respect to Te^{IV} was determined, keeping the [periodate] constant and varying [Te^{IV}] from 5.0 × 10⁻³ to 50.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. The plot of *k'* vs [Te^{IV}] was found to be a straight line passing through origin indicating first order dependence on [Te^{IV}].

The effect of [H⁺] was studied at four different temperatures 50, 55, 60 and 65°, maintaining the concentration of the reactants and ionic strength constant and varying the [H⁺] from 0.2 to 1.0 mol dm⁻³. Further increase in [H⁺] from 1.0 to 3.0 mol dm⁻³ had no perceptible effect on the rate of the reaction. The reaction could not be studied at [H⁺] less than 0.2 mol dm⁻³ because of the precipitation of Te^{IV}.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [H⁺] ON RATE OF REACTION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	<i>k'</i> (× 10 ³ , sec ⁻²)			
	50°	55°	60°	65°
0.2	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.1
0.4	1.6	2.0	2.5	3.2
0.6	1.7	2.3	3.0	3.8
0.8	1.8	2.5	3.3	4.3
1.0	1.9	2.6	3.6	4.8

Ionic strength variation studies were carried out in 0.2 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid, varying the ionic strength from 0.2 to 3.0 mol dm⁻³ using sodium perchlorate. The *k'* values were found to remain constant with the increase in ionic strength.

Havezov and Jordan⁸ summarised the most probable species of Te^{IV} at different [H⁺] and found that in the pH range 3.0–7.5 it exists as HTeO₃⁻ and in pH 3.0–1.0 mol dm⁻³ mineral acid in the form of TeO(OH)⁺ or Te(OH)₂⁺. Therefore, in the [H⁺] range employed in the present investigation Te^{IV} may be presumed to exist as TeO(OH)⁺ or its hydrated form Te(OH)₂⁺.

In the hydrogen ion concentration range 0.2–1.0 mol dm⁻³, periodate exists partly in the form of neutral H₅IO₆ and partly as H₄IO₆⁻, the latter practically disappearing from 1.0 mol dm⁻³ acid concentration onwards. Between pH 3 and 7 periodate exists only in the form of H₄IO₆⁻ or its

dehydrated form IO₃⁻ depending on the temperature⁸. From the observed constancy in rate with the increase in ionic strength and from the observed increase in rate with increase in the [H⁺] upto 1.0 mol dm⁻³ and its constancy thereafter, it may be inferred that H₅IO₆ is the reactive species involved in the oxidation of tellurium(IV).

On the basis of the experimental observations made in the present investigation the following mechanism has been proposed for the oxidation of tellurium(IV) by periodate,

This mechanism leads to the rate expression

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{H}_5\text{IO}_6]}{dt} = \frac{k_r[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}][\text{Periodate}][\text{H}^+]}{K + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (3)$$

The observed pseudo-first order rate constant (*k'*) may therefore be expressed as

$$k' = \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Periodate}]} = \frac{k_r[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}][\text{H}^+]}{K + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (4)$$

Rearranging equation (4),

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{K}{k_r[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}][\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k_r[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) predicts that the plot of 1/*k'* vs 1/[H⁺] should be a straight line with an intercept on the rate axis. When the data in Table 1 are plotted such curves (Fig. 1) are obtained, thus supporting the proposed mechanism. From the intercepts of this plot, the values of *k_r*, at 50, 55, 60 and 65° are

Fig. 1. Plots of 1/*k'* vs 1/[H⁺] at different temperatures. (1) 323, (2) 328, (3) 333 and (4) 338 K; [Te^{IV}]=1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Periodate]=1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, μ=1.0 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄).

found to be 2.2×10^{-2} , 3.3×10^{-2} , 4.8×10^{-2} and $6.9 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The activation parameters E_a and ΔS^\ddagger have been computed from these rate constants employing the linear least-squares method and found to be $68.6 \pm 6.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-54.6 \pm 20.1 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Further, from the slopes and intercepts of the plots of Fig. 1, the values of K have been computed to be 15.2×10^{-2} , 25.4×10^{-2} , 33.3×10^{-2} and 45.0×10^{-2} at 50, 55, 60 and 65° respectively. These values are in good agreement with those calculated from the spectrophotometric data³, i.e. 11.7×10^{-2} , 16.3×10^{-2} , 28.2×10^{-2} and 45.7×10^{-2} at 50, 55, 60 and 65° respectively, thus furnishing further support to the proposed mechanism.

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References

1. L. S. A. DIKSHITULU and D. SATYANARAYANA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, 38, 1848; L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, V. H. RAO and S. N. DINDI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 203; R. R. BABU, P. VANI and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 262, 1027; L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, R. R. BABU and N. S. DEVI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1988, 13, 39; L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, V. H. RAO and P. VANI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 974; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A*, 1986, 56, 7; L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, V. H. RAO and B. V. KUMAR, *Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1984, 7, 155.
2. I. HAVEZOV and N. JORDANOV, *Talanta*, 1974, 21, 1030.
3. C. E. CROUTHAMEL, A. M. HAYES and D. S. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 82.

Anodisation of Aluminium and some of its Alloys in Organic and Inorganic Acids

HESHAM MANSOUR*, MOUSTAFA H. M. ABOU-EL-WAFA,
F. M. EL-CHEIKH and K. K. KASEM

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science at Qena, Qena, Egypt
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accepted 22 July 1989

THERE are numerous reports on the anodisation of Al, Al-Mg, Al-Zn and Al-Cu in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions at different current densities^{1,2}. The films formed at low current density (50.0 A m^{-2}) are organometallic in nature while at higher values ($200-400 \text{ A m}^{-2}$), the films are hard and compact¹.

In the present work, Al metal and Al-Mn and Al-Mg alloys were anodised at 1.0 A dm^{-2} and

$30 \pm 0.10^\circ$. The acids used for anodisation were; acetic, propionic, n-butyric, maleic, oxalic, citric, tartaric, phosphoric and sulphuric acids.

Experimental

The cleaning, anodisation, corrosion tests and chemical composition of specimens (Al and Al-Mn alloy) were described in our earlier publication³. The chemical composition of Al-Mg alloy used was Al, 94.70; Mg, 5.0; Fe, 0.1; Si, 0.1; Mn, 0.1%.

Results and Discussion

The temperature-time ($\Delta T-t$) relations were obtained from the dissolution process of the anodised and non-anodised specimens as shown in Fig. 1. It is obvious that the dissolution in HCl is characterised initially by a passive period of time

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔT vs t for Al in HCl anodised in different acids: (1) acetic, (2) propionic, (3) butyric, (4) maleic, (5) tartaric, (6) oxalic, (7) citric, (8) phosphoric and (9) sulphuric.

during which only a slight increase in temperature was observed which was then followed by an increase in temperature indicating the depassivation of the metal surface and the increase in the dissolution rate.

According to Mylius⁴, the reaction number is given by the relation, $R.N. = \Delta T_m/t$, where t is the time needed for the temperature to attain a maximum and ΔT_m the maximum elevation in temperature. The values of R.N. are given in Table 1. The observed decrease of R.N. corresponds to the increase in corrosion resistance caused by the anodic treatment. On the other hand, the time needed for the temperature to reach $\Delta T_m/2$ ($t_{1/2}$) can be considered as a function of the corrosion resistance of the studied specimens. The values of $t_{1/2}$ are also given in Table 1. The specimens of Al anodised in polybasic carboxylic acids (oxalic, citric, tartaric and maleic) showed the highest values of $t_{1/2}$. This may be attributed to the gradual dissolution of the anodic film possessing a considerable thickness, which is obviously much greater than the thickness